

Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs, Cultural Game Jams, and Games through & for Culture

*Report on Insights from the Design and
Construction of Ecosystems and Game Jams*

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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START

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Executive Summary

Executive Summary

This report presents key insights from the EPIC-WE project and its design and construction of the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, Cultural Hubs, and Cultural Game Jams, along with models, methods, and tools. It explores how cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, higher education institutions, and youth can enter transformative quadruple helix partnerships and ‘meet in the middle’ by forming cultural hubs and conducting cultural game jams to co-create games through and for culture for empowered cross-sector participation. At its core, the project investigates how Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Hubs, cultural game jams, and games through and for culture can foster transformative and participatory cultural innovation ecosystems while empowering youth and sectors alike.

Key Takeaways

QH Cultural Hubs serve as a novel approach to collaborative ecosystems where HEIs, CHIs, CIs, and YCs meet in the middle to engage in co-creative processes and jointly engage cultural heritage and the (cultural) world around them, exploring collaborative opportunities and ideas, and futures for meaningful cultural-creative interactions, experiences and impact. They facilitate transformative and equal partnerships and cultural innovation but require deliberate development to ensure more equitable youth participation and long-term sustainability.

Cultural Game Jams have proven to be a robust cultural engagement and empowerment method through committed and continued collaboration by the QH Cultural Hub. The project has developed the Cultural Game Jam Kit, which includes structured phases, methods, tools, and roles, and it balances structured guidance with creative freedom, local adaptability, and glocal engagement.

Games through and for Culture are the tangible outcomes of Cultural Game Jams, which showcase the innovative conceptualisation of games in culture; through EPIC-WE, young people co-create games through and for culture, deeply connected to European values. Games through culture employ game-making as a new form of culture-making by using cultural heritage as game-making material to create alternative cultural worlds within the medium of games. Games for culture engage youth as citizens and highlight their cultural and societal reflections, engagements or transformations of their cultural world. This dual approach to games in culture offers a nuanced approach to integrating games into cultural heritage spaces and practices.

Transnational and Glocal Approaches: The project emphasises the importance of local communities while fostering global cultural exchange and innovation. The “glocal” approach enables cross-cultural collaborations and imbuing cultural game-making processes with local, regional, national, and European perspectives while continuously influencing the local cultural hubs.

Future Directions: The project identifies key areas for future development, including participatory governance models for cultural hubs, long-term mentorship for youth as culture-makers and game-makers, and policies that support the integration of cultural game jams into institutional frameworks.

EPIC-WE has demonstrated that QH Cultural Hubs, cultural game jams, game-making as culture-making, and games through and for culture significantly impact how cultural heritage is engaged with, interpreted, and reimagined. The project provides a foundation for future practice, research, and policy development in cultural participation, cross-sector collaboration, and the empowerment of youth as active partners in cultural innovation and collaboration. Moving forward, sustained efforts will be needed to refine such participatory cultural methodologies, ensure equitable access to cultural co-creation opportunities, and embed these practices within broader institutional and policy landscapes.

Lastly, the report disseminates and synthesises findings from the initial reports, including a systematic review of game jams across sectors and identification of good practices. It also includes four protocols on the cultural ecosystem framing the project, the cultural game jam methods and approaches in local sites, and the research and practical approaches. Finally, it draws on the current work-in-progress of updating and revising the four protocols towards glocal perspectives and finalising them (Winter 2025).

Introduction

01

Introduction

This report explores the theoretical and practical foundations of the **EPIC-WE** project. This EU Horizon research and innovation action project reimagines how cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, higher education institutions, and youth collaborate to engage and shape culture through game-making. EPIC-WE develops and critically examines three interconnected cultural innovation practices:

1. **Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Hubs:** QH Cultural Hubs utilise Quadruple Helix Innovation Ecosystems and Living Labs to bring together cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), creative industries (CIs), higher education institutions (HEIs), and youth citizens (YCs) in equal and transformative partnerships geared towards empowered cultural participation and innovation.
2. **Cultural Game Jams:** A novel format that merges game-making and culture-making, empowering youth as active participants in shaping culture, heritage, and society through collaborative cultural game jam processes towards creating games through and for culture.
3. **Games through and for Culture:** The outcomes of cultural game jams that engage, transform, and reimagine cultural heritage, culture, and society through games as a technology-

EPIC-WE displays how the past can inspire new creative futures through game-making and participatory culture-making through cultural heritage. The project addresses critical research and innovation gaps, particularly the value-creation of game jams and their role in embedding and expressing cultural worlds. EPIC-WE empowers sectors to come together in QH Cultural Hubs and 'jam with culture' to foster long-term engagement and impact across communities.

This report details the development and implementation of these innovations. It presents their principles, applications, and implications, providing concrete examples and insights from the project's iterative research and innovation process, along with their creative, cultural, and societal potential, and how games through and for culture can serve as both a medium for cultural storytelling and method for reimagining cultural heritage, identity, and belonging.

Methodology and Report Development Process

02

Methodology and Report Development Process

This report synthesises insights from the EPIC-WE design and construction phases of Work Package 3 (WP3), which developed ecosystems, processes, methods, and tools for implementing QH Cultural Hubs and cultural game jams (WP4). The project adopts a Design-Based Research (DBR) approach, integrating iterative cycles of analysis, design, implementation, and evaluation to produce practical, theory-informed solutions. This methodology facilitates the systematic design and testing of co-creative partnerships, cultural interventions, and the intersection of games and culture for empowered participation.

The Design and Construction Phase represented the second stage of EPIC-WE's DBR process (McKenney & Reeves, 2019), as outlined in project reports (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024b; Nørgård & Holflod, 2024c; Somers Miles et al., 2024). This phase transformed insights from WP2 into structured ecosystems and tools aimed at fostering collaboration among Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHI), Creative Industries (CI), Higher Education Institutions (HEI), and youth. Development progressed through two iterative cycles:

1. Local (DBR Round 1) – Focused on smaller-scale interventions and pilot implementations.
2. Glocal (DBR Round 2) – Expanded and refined interventions informed by previous findings and broader stakeholder involvement.

Key outcomes included the QH Cultural Hub Model and the Cultural Game Jam Kit. WP3's primary objectives were twofold:

- Developing QH Cultural Hubs to support value-driven, cross-sector co-creation and game-making by defining processes, methods, and tools for collaboration.
- Establishing protocols for local and glocal cultural game jams as DBR interventions, facilitating youth, CHI, CI, and HEI engagement. These resulted in the Cultural Game Jam format and Kit, later tested in WP4.

This report presents findings on QH Cultural Hubs, cultural game jams, and the Cultural Game Jam Kit, demonstrating how these formats foster cultural creativity, collaboration, and innovation. The final sections reflect on WP3's experiences and explore future possibilities for co-creative cultural ecosystems.

Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs

03

Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs

What do we talk about when talking about QH Cultural Hubs?

Cultural Hubs in EPIC-WE function as dynamic living laboratories tailored to the realm of culture and cultural heritage. Within the EPIC-WE project, they are established, managed, and evaluated across three European locations: Óbidos (Portugal), Hilversum (The Netherlands), and Aarhus (Denmark). Drawing on the EPIC-WE cultural adaptation of quadruple helix innovation ecosystems, these QH Cultural Hubs operate through the collaboration of four key sectors: higher education institutions, cultural heritage institutions, the creative industry, and youth citizens (for instance, the Danish QH Cultural Hub comprises Aarhus University, Filmby Aarhus, ARoS Art Museum, and youth partners). They promote cross-sector, transdisciplinary collaborations through 'meeting in the middle,' aiming to empower all partners to co-create meaningful, value-sensitive cultural innovations. The QH Cultural Hubs embody theoretical and practical innovation and cultural experimentation by translating abstract ecosystems and models into concrete, localised cultural research and innovation practices. Led by dedicated hub coordinators, QH Cultural Hubs facilitate democratic dialogue, cultural co-creation, and empowered participation - ensuring that all sectors, including youth, evolve from consultation to equal partnership. Over the first two years, continuous development, testing, and iterative refinement have evolved and strengthened the real-world practice of the QH Cultural Hubs, where partners collaboratively preserve, reimagine, and innovate cultural heritage through game-making as culture-making, ensuring lasting cultural value, impact, and support for European cultural policy objectives.

Fundamental Principles for QH Cultural Hubs

QH Cultural Hubs operate as a dynamic environment for collaboration, innovation, and transformation within the domain of culture and cultural heritage. It is characterised by continuous and affirmative engagements and reflections regarding each partner's roles, responsibilities, values, and practices. The challenge is to take on the sustained challenge of meeting in the middle to curiously and creatively think, act, and be 'otherwise' beyond one's 'native sector'. The below principles identify and determine the foundational principles for the formation and running of QH Cultural Hubs.

Principle 1: Democratising cultural innovation by including citizens and users as core partners in the QH Cultural Hub

In the QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, citizens/users are central partners in cultural research and innovation. As equal partners and active co-creators within the QH Cultural Hub and in its execution of cultural events such as Cultural Game Jams, citizens/users engage in research and innovation on an equal footing with the other helix partners. Equal participation among cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, higher education institutions and citizens/users ensures that cultural transformation and innovation remain democratic, authentic, credible, and impactful. The QH Cultural Hub model fosters democratic and participatory co-creation by embedding citizens/users at every phase, enabling them to participate meaningfully in research and innovation activities as a deliberate form of culture-making.

Principle 2: Form equal and transformative partnerships in cultural innovation

QH Cultural Hubs are intentionally designed as diverse and inclusive environments where cross-sector collaboration and co-creation flourish. They are based on the principle that each sector is an equal partner in cultural research and innovation and that each partner is open to being transformed by the others to 'think, do, and be otherwise' by transcending sectorial boundaries and methods. Each partner must embrace reciprocal transformation through the mutual integration of 'alien' knowledges, values, and meanings discourses.

Principle 3: Institutes meeting in the middle

QH Cultural Hubs deliberately establish themselves by 'meeting in the middle.' They serve as the operational space for cross-sector transformative partnerships. These meetings necessitate that all partners 'meet each other halfway' regarding vocabularies, ideas, methodologies, practices, and expectations. QH Cultural Hubs, enacted through 'meetings in the middle,' promote ongoing dynamic negotiation, enabling the reimagination and reconfiguration of cultural practices. This, in turn, demands resilience and commitment from all sector partners as it disrupts the stable and stabilises the unstable to create new forms of cultural collaboration that transcend traditional sectoral divides.

Principle 4: Practice co-creative cultural innovation and transformation for public good(s)

Innovation in QH Cultural Hubs is experimental, iterative, open-ended, and focused on co-creating cultural public good(s). By prioritising co-creation for public good(s) over purely technical, economical, or instrumental solutions, QH Cultural Hubs ensure that cultural goods and innovations remain valuable, meaningful, and freely accessible for all. Cultural innovation must serve the public good as public goods, positioning cultural QH Cultural Hubs and cultural game jams as drivers for democratic and empowered cultural participation.

Principle 5: Develop real-world, real-life QH Cultural Hubs

QH Cultural Hubs are established and operate within larger existing (global-glocal-local) cultural ecosystems. As such, QH Cultural Hubs are naturally part of and take part in the everyday real-life of real-world spaces such as museums, libraries, cultural centres, public spaces, and heritage sites. Rather than erecting external 'innovation spaces', QH Cultural Hub partners use their cultural homes to practice co-design transformation in collaboration with local citizens, users, and stakeholders. This requires that these spaces be reconfigured to be collectively occupied and acted on by the QH Cultural Hub partners, transforming and de-centring traditional institutional frameworks and spaces to allow new modes of living, acting, and being together within a shared, participatory environment.

Principle 6: Advance Empowered Participation in Culture

QH Cultural Hubs must strive to foster inclusive, diverse, and equitable participation, ensuring that all helix partners feel they are co-owners of the QH Cultural Hub space and operations and equally invited to take part in the cultural innovation decisions, activities, practices and experiences happening there. Empowered participation extends beyond being listened to or consulted, positioning every participant as a core partner and indispensable member.

QH Cultural Hubs must prioritise cultural innovation created through co-operation and co-creation and initiated from experiences of cultural imagination, agency, belonging, and respect. Success is measured by the QH Cultural Hub's ability to create a space for empowered participation among its partners and users, fostering new and potentially more empowering ways of engaging with and co-creating cultural heritage, spaces, experiences, and futures.

The full descriptions of the principles and how to operationalise them can be found in D3.2 Protocol 1.

Expanded description of QH Cultural Hubs

The QH Cultural Hubs serve as the collaborative foundation of EPIC-WE, enacted across three cultural sites in Europe: Óbidos (Portugal), Hilversum (The Netherlands), and Aarhus (Denmark), QH Cultural Hubs bring together diverse stakeholders—academia, creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, and youth—to co-create cultural experiences and knowledge through collective inquiry, problematisation, and co-desire of better collaborative and cultural futures.

The quadruple helix innovation ecosystem underpins the QH Cultural Hubs, offering a future-oriented model for cross-sector collaboration. EPIC-WE advances this by fostering creative, cultural, and democratic co-operatives—partnerships built on equality, entanglement, and non-competition (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024a).

Drawing from living labs, QH Cultural Hubs transform the theoretical framework into tangible spaces for cultural research and innovation. These hubs transcend sectoral boundaries, enabling shared, interdependent partnerships in inquiry and practice, co-desired relationships, and working between joint problematisations and innovative solutions. Each hub, physical and virtual, is guided by a hub lead who facilitates collaboration, nurtures diverse perspectives, and ensures a dynamic, inclusive environment for cultural co-creation.

During EPIC-WE's first two years (2023-25), the QH Cultural Hub model has been developed, tested, and refined through cross-sector collaboration. This dynamic process defines and evaluates partners' roles, values, and practices to harness the power of "meeting in the middle" for innovation and new ways of thinking, acting, and being. Here, hub leads play a key role in fostering democratic dialogue, ensuring all sectors stay engaged despite challenges. Central to EPIC-WE is empowered participation, extending beyond youth to all QH Cultural Hub partners. While youth engagement emphasises cultural and creative belonging, the project fosters civic and cultural imagination across all sectors.

Early research from EPIC-WE's work packages revealed participation imbalances, especially in youth involvement. While youth contribute to cultural projects like game jams, their role in decision-making remains limited, often confined to consultation rather than co-creation. Initiatives like youth advisory boards mark progress but highlight the need for more significant structural changes in how participation is understood and practised. Recognising youth as equal partners—rather than passive participants—is essential for future cultural innovation. By embracing this shift, QH Cultural Hubs become dynamic spaces where culture is explored, preserved, and reimaged through participatory research and innovation.

Shaping Cultural Futures: Processes, Results, and Horizons

At their core, QH Cultural Hubs serve as collaborative ecosystems where knowledge, creativity, and cultural heritage converge to drive imagination and innovation within the cultural domain. The project's research and collaborations illustrate that successful collaboration relies on dynamic processes that facilitate structured knowledge exchange and emergent creativity, supporting inclusivity, accessibility, and democratic inquiry and participation. Rather than enforcing rigid frameworks, the most effective QH Cultural Hub processes nurture adaptive environments that encourage open-ended exploration while adopting the guiding principles and preserving a shared purpose. This balance guarantees that QH Cultural Hubs remain responsive to changing contextual, cultural, and societal needs and continue to yield meaningful, valuable, and impactful research and innovations.

Looking ahead, the future of QH Cultural Hubs lies in refining models that support long-term collaboration and cultural co-creation. Key areas for development include strengthening participatory governance structures, expanding access to resources and opportunities across sectors – particularly involving youth, and fostering environments of cultural experiences, play, imagination and creation (the four phases of the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jams). As cultural ecosystems, QH Cultural Hubs must facilitate the co-creation of knowledge and cultural-creative outcomes (e.g. Cultural Game Jams or games through and for culture) and serve as incubators for new ways of thinking, engaging, and envisioning cultural heritage practices and futures. QH Cultural Hubs can shape more inclusive and transformative cultural landscapes by continually evolving through collaboration, reflection, and shared agency.

Cultural Game Jams

04

Cultural Game Jams

Game-making as culture-making: Cultural Game Jams

A central activity within the EPIC-WE project is developing, facilitating, and refining cultural game jams for youth citizens (ages 16-25). In these game jams, participants create games inspired by cultural heritage, engaging in co-creation processes that position game-making as a form of culture-making. By collaborating with peers from diverse backgrounds, young citizens (YCs) actively shape the future of cultural heritage by creating games that reflect and promote culture. The overarching aim of Cultural Game Jams is to foster empowered participation, enabling YCs to cultivate a stronger sense of cultural agency and belonging. By involving youth in the reimagining, reconfiguring, and creating culture through cultural heritage, the project equips YCs with the imagination for culture-making and the skills for game-making, allowing them to engage with cultural and societal challenges in new and empowering ways.

EPIC-WE explores the potential and values of Cultural Game Jams with several key objectives. First, the project aims to empower youth to become co-creators of European culture by involving them in game-making as a form of cultural creation. This process enables collaboration between youth and partners in the creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, and higher education domains within the QH Cultural Hubs. The project further bridges the domains of games and culture, encouraging young people's empowered participation through the Cultural Game Jam format and processes. Creating games through and for culture that engage, reflect, and innovate cultural heritage enriches both the gaming and cultural sectors, highlighting the potential for games to serve as genuine cultural expressions and interpretations. Here, the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jams Kit facilitates the Cultural Game Jams and provides youth with the methods and resources to create games through and for culture.

Fundamental Principles for Cultural Game Jams

Seven fundamental principles can be synthesised from the previous R&I efforts of the EPIC-WE project and its conceptualisation of QH Cultural Hubs, Cultural Game Jams, and games through and for culture. These principles guide the Cultural Game Jams and their accompanying Cultural Game Jam Kit:

Principle 1: Three ways to run Cultural Game Jams

Cultural Game Jams embrace a structured yet adjustable approach to game-making as culture-making, offering three levels of adaptability:

- **Fixed**, where Cultural Game Jam elements are determined at the project or organisational level
- **Flexible**, where the QH Cultural Hub tailor the process to local needs
- **Freeform**, where youth shape their creative and collaborative journey based on the Cultural Game Jam Kit.

These levels operate within a minimum viable model, balancing guidance and exploration. The Cultural Game Jam phases - Experience, Play, Imagine, Create - provide a straightforward yet open-ended process, allowing participants to engage with cultural themes and heritage by creating games through and for culture. Transition tools like the Ideation Wheel and Expert Council help participants transition from one phase to the next while refining ideas and integrating feedback and decisions.

Principle 2: Aim for cultural participation, co-creation, and empowerment

Cultural Game Jams position game-making as an act of cultural imagination and creation, where youth are not just receivers or consumers of heritage but active creators and contributors to shaping its future. Participants engage in a co-creative process that positions game-making as a new form of culture-making through which youth create and showcase games through and for culture. These games directly engage cultural heritage, using it as an empowering medium for game-making. This participatory approach fosters a sense of ownership and belonging, allowing youth to engage, reinterpret, and comment on cultural heritage through game-making in ways that reflect their own experiences and identities. By designing games that reflect their lived experiences, values, and collective imaginaries, participants develop a stronger sense of agency and belonging in cultural heritage and within cultural environments.

Principle 3: Foster cultural curiosity and creativity

Cultural Game Jams cultivate an environment where curiosity and creativity drive cultural exploration, encouraging youth to become culture-makers through cultural storytelling and game design. The game-making process fosters deep engagement with past, present, and future cultural narratives by allowing participants to experiment, remix, and reimagine cultural heritage by creating games through and for culture. Through Cultural Game Jams, culture is not a static artefact of the past but an evolving and participatory practice that youth actively shape by creating cultural experiences, interactions, and expressions.

Principle 4: Cultivate an "epic we" through Cultural Game Jams

Cultural Game Jams are designed to cultivate a sense of community and collective creativity that transcends the individual to foster an experience of becoming part of an "epic we" in cultural heritage. This approach requires creating conditions encouraging collaboration, relational engagement and shared cultural exploration, where differences interact generatively rather than competitively. By embracing tensions and dissimilarities as opportunities for cultural curiosity and co-creation, Cultural Game Jams become more than game-making events – they serve as transformative cultural environments that nurture engaged participation, cultural empowerment, and collective culture-making.

Principle 5: Practice value-sensitive and reflective game-making

At the heart of Cultural Game Jams is a commitment to value-sensitive cultural design, where cultural, ethical, and societal considerations shape the game-making process. Participants are encouraged to critically engage and examine themes such as citizenship, European identity, and cultural heritage's evolving and participatory nature. And to engage this through a co-creative approach and the creation of games through and for culture. Participants explore how cultural heritage and values are embedded in and expressed through game mechanics, interactions,

narratives, and aesthetics. This, in turn, fosters a deeper awareness of how games, through and for culture, can function as a method for cultural critique, reflectivity, expression, and empowerment.

Principle 6: Engage game-making as cultural innovation and interpretation

Cultural Game Jams challenge more audience-oriented notions of cultural heritage by engaging game-making as a powerful method for action-oriented cultural engagement. Rather than approaching heritage as something to be preserved, admired, or consumed, Cultural Game Jams invite participants to reimagine, remix, remediate, and recreate cultural works and narratives in their games through and for culture. This approach highlights the potential of games as interactive systems and experiences. As such, they can provoke thought, spark dialogue, and interactively engage audiences as players with and within cultural heritage. By embedding cultural inquiry, interpretation, and innovation into the game-making process, Cultural Game Jams contribute to a broader recognition of games' potential as culture and within cultural heritage.

Principle 7: Create games through and for culture and cultural transformation

Cultural Game Jams position game-making as a reflection of and active engagement with culture, resulting in the creation of games through and for culture. By embedding historical, imaginative, and societal themes in games and inviting game-makers to engage with heritage through cultural transformation, Cultural Game Jams results in games through and for culture that serve as immersive cultural storytelling forms. This dual focus on games through culture (exploring and incorporating cultural heritage as game-making material towards new interactive cultural expressions) and games for culture (imagining and enacting values, identities, and collective responsibility in culture and society) ensures that Cultural Game Jams and their resulting games are not only about transmission of cultural heritage but are also integral to its ongoing transformation and evolution.

The Cultural Game Jam Kit for facilitating Cultural Game Jams

The Cultural Game Jam Kit is a core outcome of the EPIC-WE project and facilitates the design and execution of Cultural Game Jams. The Cultural Game Jam Kit contains the following essential elements:

- The **EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Process Model** is a simple visual guide that outlines a Cultural Game Jam's phases, methods, and categories. It provides an easy-to-follow structure and roadmap.
- The **E-P-I-C Phases** divide the Cultural Game Jam process into four stages: Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create. The stages focus on game-making as culture-making towards creating games through and for culture.
- The **W-E Dimensions** emphasise the Cultural Game Jams focus on cultural worlds and empowered participation, encouraging youth to engage with cultural heritage, identity, and transformation.

- The **EPIC-WE Categories** focus on the central domains of Cultural Game Jam - Citizenship, Values, Culture, and Games - mirroring the four participating sectors in the QH Cultural Hubs. The categories support youth in creating value-sensitive games through and for culture.
- The **EPIC-WE Transition Tools** help youth transition from one phase to the next, leading to their final games through and for culture showcase at the Cultural Game Jam Expo. In Experience, it is the Ideation Wheel; in Play, the Expert Council; in Imagine, the Playtest; and in Create, the Log and Pitch.
- The **EPIC-WE Methods Collection** contains a range of concrete Cultural Game Jam methods for each of the E-P-I-C phases to facilitate the creation of games through and for culture.

A Cultural Game Jam is an immersive, co-creative activity where youth citizens (ages 16-25) create games inspired by cultural heritage. The game-making process encourages participants to co-create games through and for cultures with diverse perspectives and peers. Through collaborating in Cultural Game Jams towards the final EXPO of their games through and for culture, youth are positioned as game-makers and culture-makers, actively engaged in shaping new identities and futures of cultural heritage. As such, one main goal of Cultural Game Jams is to empower youth by nurturing a sense of belonging in culture, cultural heritage, and Europe, enabling them to engage with past, present, and future cultural and societal engagements and transformations.

Cultural Game Jams are not just Game Jams

By involving youth in co-creating culture, the project emphasises curiosity, creativity, agency, and the potential of games as a form of cultural expression and interpretation – as remixing, remediating, repositioning, and recreating. Through collaboration with creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, and higher education institutions within Cultural Hubs, Cultural Game Jams aims to merge the domains of games and culture, offering youth a platform to develop cultural empowerment, creativity, and innovation. The project challenges traditional views of cultural heritage by recognising games as a valid form of cultural expression, thus enriching both the gaming and cultural sectors. The EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit supports these efforts by providing the tools, processes, and methods for organising and facilitating Cultural Game Jams, ensuring youth have the necessary guidance and help to create meaningful and empowering games that reflect and innovate upon cultural heritage.

Cultural Game Jams foster a sense of cultural community. As such, the Cultural Game Jams of EPIC-WE extend the traditional concepts and format of game jams by emphasising cultural imagination, ideation, and transformation, offering new culture-oriented approaches to game development. As discussed in the EPIC-WE Systematic Literature (Costa et al., 2024a; Costa et al., 2024b), the Cultural Game Jam approach represents a novel way to connect game-making with cultural and societal inquiry and engagement.

As evident from the analyses from the first round of Cultural Game Jams in 2024, a key insight is that they require thoughtful planning and facilitation that considers inclusive, pluriversal, and transversal design approaches to ensure accessibility, equity, and both meaningful and empowered participation, especially regarding youth though also connected to QH Cultural Hub collaborations and synergies. Inclusive design (ID) prioritises human-centred strategies that cater to the broadest possible range of users, particularly those often overlooked in conventional design processes, fostering adaptability, innovation, and self-determination (Collier, 2020).

Pluriversal design (PD), by contrast, recognises the coexistence of multiple, locally rooted perspectives, seeking to balance power inequalities and enable epistemic participation, particularly among marginalised groups such as the youth citizens – when viewing youth in connection to its collaborative counterparts in the QH Cultural Hubs – in EPIC-WE (Escobar, 2017). This approach reframes design as a relational and collaborative practice that values trust, long-term commitments, and attentiveness to power dynamics (Scheel et al., 2019). Transversal design (TD) extends these ideas by rejecting both totalising unity and fragmented individualism, instead envisioning design as a space where tensions across different perspectives can generate creative encounters and an emergent sense of collective identity—an epic “we” of radical creativity (Hsu, 2021). By exploring these approaches and perspectives in the planning and execution of Cultural Game Jams, the project fosters innovation ecosystems that support sustainable, inclusive, and co-creative cultural interventions. It ensures that participants' diversity and multiplicity are acknowledged and actively shape the process and its outcomes.

Games *through* and *for* culture

05

Games through and for culture

Games through and for culture result from the Cultural Game Jam Kit and Cultural Game Jams. These games explore, reimagine, and express intangible and tangible cultural heritage.

Games through culture

Games through culture utilise cultural heritage as innovative game-making material to enable new aesthetic expressions, actualisations, and remediations of cultural heritage and game design. Cultural Game Jams targeting games through culture allow youth to engage directly with tangible cultural heritage to reimagine, remix, and recreate it as a game shaped by cultural heritage. Instead of using games to communicate or teach about cultural heritage or to interpret, critique, or innovate on societal issues, this model frames cultural heritage as transformative and innovative game-making material and games as entities that can be reimaged and co-created with cultural heritage. Notably, the emphasis on games through culture highlights youth's deep integration of cultural heritage into their games, serving as a means towards empowered participation in culture.

Key points of games through culture include:

- Tangible cultural heritage is a medium for experiencing, engaging with, imagining, and creating, leading to cultural heritage transformations or reinterpretations through games.
- Youth “jam” with cultural heritage—concretely and directly—by participating in game jamming within cultural environments such as galleries, libraries, archives, and museums, using the cultural assets they house as materials in their game-making processes.
- Cultural heritage is reinterpreted and transformed through game development, enabling young people to connect with and contribute to heritage in novel, participatory, and interactive ways.
- Cultural heritage institutions broaden their roles beyond curation and exhibition, actively participating in co-creating cultural gameplay interactions and experiences alongside young people.

This approach encourages cultural heritage institutions to invite and enable youth to become culture-makers through being game-makers. This further acknowledges games through culture and their unique empowering potential to culture and cultural heritage. By embracing games as a creative and innovative medium, these institutions foster widened participation and provide opportunities for young people to contribute directly to the preservation, transformation and evolution of cultural heritage.

Games for culture

Games for culture engage broader cultural and societal contexts by creating games with and for cultural value, transformation, and empowered participation. Cultural Game Jams targeting games for culture invite youth to engage directly with intangible cultural and societal issues to showcase how culture or society might be reimaged, remixed, and recreated through games. As such, games for culture aim for value-driven or -sensitive game-making towards cultural transformation, new cultural experiences, and empowered cultural citizenship and belonging.

Games for culture offer a dynamic way for young people to actively participate in shaping culture and society through game design. This approach invites youth to engage with existing cultural narratives and empowers them to create entirely new ones. By collaborating with cultural heritage institutions and the creative industries, young people become cultural co-creators, using the medium of games to express their identities and perspectives and address cultural or societal challenges. Notably, games for culture frame and emphasise the vital cultural and societal issues connected to identity, belonging, and citizenship.

Key elements of games for culture include:

- Game-making is not just a tool for engaging tangible cultural heritage but an approach towards creating new cultural forms and expressions inspired by cultural heritage and for cultural or societal transformation and empowerment.
- Youth become co-creative culture-makers by creatively reshaping cultural and societal narratives, issues, or experiences.
- Cultural heritage institutions facilitate cultural transformation, providing inspiring and engaging game-making environments for youth.
- Game-making becomes a cultural or societal dialogic medium for exploring identity, belonging, citizenship and the role of European culture and values in new, interactive ways.
- Game-making is an explorative and experimenting artistic and cultural practice. It fosters innovation, encourages diverse youth participation, and empowers youth through cultural heritage to create games for cultural-societal ideas, issues, and futures.

Principles for making games through and for culture

A result of the ongoing R&I efforts within the EPIC-WE project is six fundamental principles that guide game-making as culture-making in Cultural Game Jams, which result in youth making games through and for culture:

Principle 1: Games for societal and cultural agency

Games should not merely preserve or transmit cultural or societal issues but actively engage players in critical-creative reflections and engagements with them. By positioning game-making as a collaborative act of cultural and societal exploration and expression, games become mediums for reinterpreting history, questioning societal norms, and envisioning alternative cultural and societal futures. This means that youth are scaffolded and empowered to make games as a form of culture-making, which empowers gameplayers to explore and reflect on cultural heritage and values, enabling cultural and societal agency.

Principle 2: Games as reflections and expressions of living cultural heritage

Rather than static representations of tangible cultural heritage, games should be designed as dynamic, living transformations, reflections and expressions of cultural heritage. This implies that game-making is in and of itself a cultural practice that enables heritage to be preserved, reimagined, and transformed through the creation of games through culture. As such, games through culture are immersive and interactive extensions of cultural heritage and storytelling that embrace the fluid and evolving nature of cultural identity and belonging. This ensures that game-makers and game-players do not just 'spectate' cultural heritage but 'interactively' contribute to its ongoing evolution.

Principle 3: Games empowering participation through and for culture

Game-making can enable cultural empowerment and belonging through games' unique cultural and artistic potentials as mediums *through* culture (emphasising heritage) and *for* culture (emphasising society).

Principle 4: Facilitate cultural-creative feedback and the development of playable prototypes

Develop early prototypes to test game design and integrate cultural values, heritage, narratives, aesthetics, themes or problems profoundly and meaningfully. Prototyping allows continuous and early iteration to refine game concepts, cultural heritage significance, and cultural/societal engagement. Ensure multiple debrief sessions and feedback loops from experts, mentors, and facilitators to support Cultural Game Jam groups in creating genuinely engaging, transformative, or innovative games through and for culture.

Principle 5: Scaffold cultural relevance and importance

The QH Cultural Hubs should collaborate to create culturally relevant local and glocal themes in the Cultural Game Jams and their game- and culture-making processes. These themes should not be afterthoughts but directly engage tangible and/or intangible cultural heritage and be drivers of the game concept, cultural narrative, interactive design, and gameplay experience.

Principle 6: Empower game-making as culture-making narratives and identities

The Cultural Game Jams focus the game-making process on designing cultural narratives and identities that allow both game-makers and game-players empowerment and belonging in culture through becoming active participants in shaping cultural heritage, culture, and society through engaging with the experiences, values, and worlds of games through and for culture. By approaching, adopting, and reconfiguring these principles for games through and for culture to local – and glocal – contexts, the Cultural Game Jam Kit invites, scaffolds, and inspires youth to create games that preserve, transform, and innovate culture through the creation of games through and for culture.

Between Preservation and Transformation: Comparing games through and for culture

Games are more than cultural artefacts; they are dynamic worlds that shape, reflect, and transmit values, identities, and worldviews. They foster inclusion and exclusion, influencing ethical perspectives, belonging, and civic engagement—especially for youth, who are both players and potential creators.

International research underscores games' transformative potential, promoting social inclusion (Stewart et al., 2013), global citizenship and empathy (Bachen et al., 2012), and ethical reflection (Sicart, 2011). Initiatives like games for good and games for change demonstrate how games cultivate diversity (Plass et al., 2015), create communal spaces (Schrier, 2021; Gee, 2005), and empower marginalised voices (Grace & Leonard, 2018). As cultural products, games stand alongside literature, film, and music (Raessens, 2006), encoding worldviews and shaping identity (Muriel, 2021). Since 72% of European youth (15–24) engage with games (ISFE, 2021), their role in personal, professional, and civic life is significant.

In EPIC-WE, youth create games that mediate, preserve, and transform cultural heritage (Eriksson et al., 2024b). A key aspect of the project is its dual vision of game development through cultural game jams—as both games through culture and games for culture.

Both concepts and models—games through culture and games for culture—focus on game-making as a powerful tool for youth participation and cultural transformation. However, they do so from slightly different perspectives, and the following section thus compares the approaches.

- **Games through culture** use cultural heritage as innovative game-making material to enable new aesthetic expressions, actualisations and remediations of cultural heritage and game design. Cultural Game Jams targeting games through culture enable youth to engage directly with tangible cultural heritage to reimagine, remix, and recreate it as a game made *through* cultural heritage.
- **Games for culture** engage broader cultural and societal contexts by creating games with and for cultural value, transformation, and empowered participation. Cultural Game Jams targeting games for culture invite youth to engage directly with intangible cultural and societal issues to showcase how culture or society might be reimaged, remixed, and recreated through games. As such, games for culture aim for value-driven or –sensitive game-making towards cultural transformation, new cultural experiences, and empowered cultural citizenship and belonging.

Game-making plays a crucial role in cultural participation, interpretation, and empowerment. The games through culture and games for culture approaches offer a comprehensive vision for how Cultural Game Jams can preserve, engage with, and innovate cultural heritage. This fosters inclusive, participatory practices where youth actively shape cultural identity and belonging.

Designing games through and for culture means embedding cultural heritage, societal themes, and value-sensitive perspectives into mechanics, narratives, and aesthetics. This process turns

game-making into a distinct form of culture-making, allowing creators and players to experience, reflect on, and engage with cultural expressiveness.

Research and experiences from the first six Cultural Game Jams show that classifying a game as through or for culture depends on how deeply it integrates cultural, societal, and ethical themes. Many youth-created games tackle contemporary issues like climate change, racism, or inequality, making them games for culture as they critique and engage with societal values. Conversely, games through culture focus on tangible heritage, drawing from museums, archives, and historical sites to bring cultural traditions and artefacts to life.

Retrospectives and Imaginarities

06

Retrospectives and Imaginaries

Experience and Imagination: Ecosystems, Formats, Outcomes

The EPIC-WE project has showcased the transformative potential of cultural game jams, QH Cultural Hubs, and games through and for culture in fostering new cultural and educational ecosystems. Throughout the project, these interventions have enabled transdisciplinary collaborations across institutions and sectors, empowered youth participation, and reimagined cultural heritage as a dynamic and participatory process practice.

Reflecting on the experiences across Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos, we observe that the quadruple helix model has been instrumental in fostering sustainable partnerships among higher education institutions (HEIs), cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), creative industries (CIs), and youth citizens (YCs). These hubs have provided structured experimentation spaces, encouraging cross-sector knowledge exchange and co-creation. However, challenges have emerged, including imbalances in youth participation and institutional power dynamics, necessitating continuous refinement of participatory frameworks.

Cultural game jams have emerged as an effective method for engaging youth in cultural production. These formats blend game design with cultural storytelling and heritage reinterpretation, empowering young creators as active participants in shaping cultural narratives. However, sustaining engagement beyond the event format remains an ongoing challenge. Future iterations may concentrate on extended mentorship programmes and digital infrastructures that support long-term participation and knowledge sharing.

Games through and for culture have shown their ability to mediate, preserve, and transform cultural heritage. The spectrum between games for culture (emphasising societal reflection and problematisation) and games through culture (focusing on heritage reinterpretation) has provided a valuable framework for understanding the impact of game-based cultural interventions. Further integration of these concepts into institutional practices and policies will be necessary to ensure a lasting effect and cultural impact.

Local – Glocal – Global: Transnational Influences and Experiments

Cultural Game Jams within EPIC-WE are designed as interventions that operate across local, glocal, and global levels within a cultural innovation ecosystem. Initially, Cultural Game Jams are developed in local QH Cultural Hubs, where participants engage with community and context-specific cultural heritage, societal issues, and creative industries. These local game jams emphasise place-based practices, involving local stakeholders and focusing on their regions' unique cultural and historical contexts. However, as the project evolves, it introduces the concept of the "glocal" game jam—an approach that blends local and global influences. This approach acknowledges that while global trends shape game development, they remain deeply rooted in regional cultures, policies, and identities. Research on Nordic game policies (Sotamaa et al., 2020) highlights how countries such as Finland, Norway, and Sweden integrate artistic and innovation strategies with cultural preservation, showcasing how local policies influence global game

development. Similarly, game jams have been employed to preserve indigenous Sami culture (Kultima & Laiti, 2019), demonstrating how co-creative processes can support cultural identity. Within EPIC-WE, this interplay between local and global perspectives is a key feature of the Cultural Game Jam model, drawing from recognising that cultural expression and innovation emerge from the continuous exchange between these levels. In the systematic literature review of EPIC-WE, Costa et al. (2024a) explore how local cultural values continue to shape game development, even within the globalised industry. They highlight the dynamic exchange between local and global influences, where regional cultures inform broader frameworks and global trends and, in turn, influence local practices. This "glocal" perspective underscores the importance of regional strategies in fostering diverse and culturally rich game development on a global scale.

The concept of "glocal" culture, derived from the merging of "global" and "local," reflects how global influences adapt to and reshape local cultural practices—and vice versa. Rather than viewing global and local as opposites, they are mutually constitutive, constantly shaping one another dynamically (Roudometof, 2015).

In the context of game jams, cultural identity and local storytelling are infused with global perspectives, making Cultural Game Jams both locally significant and globally relevant. This approach is particularly important for youth culture and citizenship, where global trends in gaming and digital expression interact with local lived experiences, fostering new forms of cultural participation (Kjeldgaard & Askegaard, 2005). EPIC-WE's QH Cultural Hubs—Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos—have explored these dynamics, reflecting on how a glocal game jam can create value by facilitating cultural exchange, addressing both local and global challenges and making game-making a more inclusive and reflective practice. By adopting a glocal perspective, Cultural Game Jams encourage young creators to think globally while acting locally, fostering cultural awareness, creative agency, and the reimagining of heritage through digital play.

To strengthen the glocal dimension of Cultural Game Jams, the QH Cultural Hubs have identified and experimented with guiding principles that integrate local cultural expressions with global themes and collaborative practices. These principles are intended to ensure that Cultural Game Jams reflect local cultural heritage and societal issues and facilitate meaningful connections between participants across different regions.

By fostering a dynamic exchange of ideas across regional and national boundaries, these principles support the development of locally grounded and globally interconnected Cultural Game Jam activities and processes.

Merging Global and Local Themes

- Cultural Game Jams incorporate global themes—such as pressing societal or cultural issues—that are shared across all hubs but approached in and adapted to local contexts.
- Simultaneously, local themes—rooted in specific cultural traditions, histories, or community challenges—could be applied in glocal processes, where hubs engage with and reinterpret each other's cultural narratives.

Encouraging Collaboration Across Hubs

- Shared challenges are designed to pass between teams in different countries, fostering iterative co-creation.
- Asynchronous exchange is supported, allowing participants to give and receive feedback across different time zones, processes, and contexts, ensuring sustained engagement beyond the event itself.
- Synchronous exchange should also be encouraged through live interactions, such as collaborative game design sessions, playtesting, and final expos where game prototypes are showcased.

Building Empowering Networks and Participatory Communities

- Forming and enabling youth advisory boards to empower youth as creators to take active roles in shaping the direction of Cultural Game Jams, providing them with relevant scaffolding to support their self-directed goals and processes.
- Engaging youth participants in pre-event discussions to cultivate anticipation and investment in the event's themes and outcomes.
- Establishing mentorship programs and expert sessions across hubs can provide participants with structured guidance and transdisciplinary insights.

Creating a Sustainable Digital Infrastructure

- A shared online space (such as dynamic online communities) should be developed to facilitate long-term collaboration and relationships. This enables youth participants from different hubs and cultural worlds to exchange ideas, showcase prototypes, strengthen European creative networks, and explore youth empowerment in their own collectives.

Implementation of these principles is systematically assessed during the EPIC-WE project, determining their effectiveness and influence in supporting and enabling a shared sense of identity and belonging, participation, and collaboration among diverse European youth. Key areas of inquiry include:

1. Comparing the impact of synchronous vs. asynchronous collaboration on creativity and engagement.
2. Exploring how participants from different cultural backgrounds interpret and contribute to shared themes.
3. Assessing the role of virtual versus in-person interactions in shaping the Cultural Game Jam experiences.
4. Investigating how local reinterpretations of global themes influence the development of value-driven, meaningful and innovative games through and for culture

Ultimately, these glocal interventions seek to transform Cultural Game Jams into cultural and creative exchange and empowerment hubs where young people can navigate the intersection of local heritage and global discourse collaboratively. By incorporating these guiding principles, EPIC-WE, research and innovation hubs, and communities beyond the project can strive to ensure that Cultural Game Jams remain inclusive, reflective, and deeply connected to the evolving landscape of European cultural participation, innovation, and empowerment.

A key learning from EPIC-WE has been the interplay between local cultural expressions and global game design perspectives and their diverse connections to and influences by values, societal and cultural citizenship, and empowered participation. By integrating a “glocal” approach, the project continues to examine and demonstrate how Cultural Game Jams can foster meaningful cross-cultural exchanges while maintaining local specificity and context sensitivity. The QH Cultural Hubs experiment with models that allow for adapting global themes to local cultural contexts, ensuring relevance and inclusivity.

As we move towards the future, challenges remain in balancing institutional frameworks with the organic and experimental nature of cultural game jams and co-creative and participatory engagement in the QH Cultural Hubs. The continued evolution of these models will require an openness to rethinking cultural participation, designing more inclusive and sustainable engagement structures, and fostering ongoing dialogue between youth, cultural institutions, and creative industries.

Literature and Resources

07

Literature and Resources

Bachen, C. M., Hernández-Ramos, P. F., & Raphael, C. (2012). Simulating REAL LIVES: Promoting global empathy and interest in learning through simulation games. *Simulation & Gaming*, 43(4), 437–460.

Bogost, I. (2010). *Persuasive games: The expressive power of videogames*. MIT Press.

Collier, A. (2020). Inclusive Design and Design Justice: Strategies to Shape Our Classes and Communities. EDUCAUSE. <https://er.educause.edu/articles/2020/10/inclusive-design-and-design-justice-strategies-to-shape-our-classes-and-communities>

Costa, C., Fernandes, P., Nunes, I., Gonçalves, M., & Fonseca, M. (2024a). State of the Art in game jams and game-making co-creation practices amongst Cultural Heritage Institutions, Creative Industries, Higher Education Institutions and Youth Citizens. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14654424>

Costa, C., Fernandes, P., Nunes, I., Gonçalves, M., & Fonseca, M. (2024b). Report on good practices - Game jams and game-making co-creation practices amongst Cultural Heritage Institutions, Creative Industries, Higher Education Institutions and Youth Citizens. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14654105>

Criado, T. S., & Estalella, A. (2018). Introduction Experimental Collaborations. In A. Estalella & T. Criado (Ed.), *Experimental Collaborations: Ethnography through Fieldwork Devices* (pp. 1–30). Berghahn Books. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781785338540-004>

Eriksson, E., Holflod, K., & Nørgård, R. T. (2024a). Jamming with Culture – Piloting Cultural Game Jam with Youth. In *Proceedings of the 23rd Annual ACM Interaction Design and Children Conference (IDC '24)* (pp. 945–950). Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3628516.3659424>

Eriksson, E., Holflod, K., & Nørgård, R. T. (2024b). Creative toying with cultural heritage in game jams. In *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Game Jams, Hackathons and Game Creation Events (ICGJ '24)* (pp. 9–16). Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3697789.3697795>

Eriksson, E., Costa, C., Goncalves, M., Nunes, I., Groen, M., Niederer, S., Holflod, K., & Nørgård, R. T. (2025). Cultural game jams with youth: A multiple-site case study. In *Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI EA '25)*, April 26-May 1, 2025, Yokohama, Japan (8 pages). Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3706599.3706667>

Escobar, A. (2017). *Designs for the Pluriverse: Radical Interdependence, Autonomy, and the Making of Worlds*. Duke University Press.

Fox, J., & Tang, W. Y. (2014). Sexism in online video games: The role of conformity to masculine norms and social dominance orientation. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 33, 314–320.

Gee, J. P. (2005). Why video games are good for your soul: Pleasure and learning. Common Ground.

Gonçalves, M., Nunes, I., Fernandes, P., & Costa, C. (2024). What is “Learning” in Serious Game Jams? A Systematic Literature Review. In Proceedings of the 18th European Conference on Games Based Learning, 18(1), 304–311. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecgbl.18.1.2673>

Gray, K. L., & Leonard, D. J. (Eds.). (2018). Woke gaming: Digital challenges to oppression and social injustice. University of Washington Press.

Holfod, K., & Nørgård, R. T. (2024). Crafting Culture: Aarhus’ EPIC-WE Game Jam Connects Youth and Culture. <https://epic-we.eu/crafting-culture-aarhus-epic-we-game-jam-connects-youth-and-culture/>

Holfod, K., Nørgård, R. T., & Eriksson, E. (2024). Community, Socialisation, and Empowerment in Cultural Game Jams with Youth Citizens. In Proceedings of the 18th European Conference on Games Based Learning, 18(1), 395–402. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecgbl.18.1.2812>

Hsu, C. (2021). Transversal Design: Glimpsing the emergent whole, with the trouble. RSD10 Symposium. TU Delft, Netherlands.

ISFE (2021). 2021 Key Facts about the European video games sector. <https://bit.ly/3EpXU5k>

Kjeldgaard, D., & Askegaard, S. (2006). The Glocalization of Youth Culture: The Global Youth Segment as Structures of Common Difference. The Journal of Consumer Research, 33(2), 231–247. <https://doi.org/10.1086/506304>

Koppelman, W., & Lennaerts, K. (2024). Protocol 4: EPIC-WE Practical Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Local Sites (Initial protocol). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13886315>

Kultima, A., & Laiti, O. (2019). Sami Game Jam – Learning, Exploring, Reflecting and Sharing Indigenous Culture through Game Jamming. Proceedings of the 2019 DiGRA International Conference: Game, Play and the Emerging Ludo-Mix (pp. 97). http://www.digra.org/wp-content/uploads/digital-library/DiGRA_2019_paper_367.pdf

Luz, F., Almeida, W., Fernandes, P., & Fonseca, M. (2024). Cultural Game Jam Model: A Quadruple Helix Intervention. In Proceedings of the 18th European Conference on Games Based Learning, 18(1), 46–54. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecgbl.18.1.2642>

Massanari, A. (2017). #Gamergate and The Fappening: How Reddit’s algorithm, governance, and culture support toxic technocultures. New Media & Society, 19(3), 329–346.

Muriel, D. (2021). Video games and identity formation in contemporary society. In The Oxford Handbook of Sociology and Digital Media.

Nørgård, R. T., & Holfod, K. (2024a). Meeting in the middle: Cultural co-creation, transformative partnerships, and ecosystems for public good. Educational Philosophy and Theory, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2024.2384722>

Nørgård, R. T., & Holflod, K. (2024b). Protocol 1: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Ecosystems and Cultural Hubs (Initial protocol). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14161345>

Nørgård, R. T., & Holflod, K. (2024c). Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit: EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Processes, Phases, Methods, and Tools (Initial protocol). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14161689>

Paul, C. A. (2018). *The toxic meritocracy of video games: Why gaming culture is the worst*. University of Minnesota Press.

Plass, J. L., Homer, B. D., & Kinzer, C. K. (2015). Foundations of game-based learning. *Educational Psychologist*, 50(4), 258–283.

Raessens, J. (2006). Playful identities, or the ludification of culture. *Games and Culture*, 1(1), 52–57.

Roudometof, V. (2015). The Glocal and Global Studies. *Globalizations*, 12(5), 774–787. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14747731.2015.1016293>

Scheel, S., Grommé, F., Ruppert, E., Ustek-Spilda, F., Cakici, B., & Takala, V. (2019). Doing a transversal method: developing an ethics of care in a collaborative research project. *Global Networks: A Journal of Transnational Affairs*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/glob.12263>

Schütz, F., Heidingsfelder, M. L., & Schraudner, M. (2019). Co-shaping the future in quadruple helix innovation systems: uncovering public preferences toward participatory research and innovation. *She Ji: The Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation*, 5(2), 128–146.

Schrier, K. K. (2021). Using games for empathy, compassion, and care. In *Teaching in the Game-Based Classroom* (pp. 136–150). Eye on Education.

Sicart, M. (2011). *The ethics of computer games*. MIT Press.

Somers Miles, R., Koppelman, W., Lennaerts, K., Sabine Niederer, De Gaetano, C., Groen, M., Dockett, A., Eriksson, E., & Holflod, K. (2024). Protocol 3: EPIC-WE Research Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Local Sites. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13886222>

Stewart, J., Bleumers, L., Van Looy, J., Mariën, I., All, A., Schurmans, D., Willaert, K., De Grove, F., Jacobs, A., & Misuraca, G. (2013). *The Potential of Digital Games for Empowerment and Social Inclusion of Groups at Risk of Social and Economic Exclusion: Evidence and Opportunity for Policy*. EUR 25900. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

Wiinstedt Tscherning, R., & Ayaydin, B. (2024). First Policy Briefs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13882418>

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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